

Crystallisation Behaviour of the Tsokar Lake Brine at 50°

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Tsokar lake brine has been taken up to establish its crystallisation behaviour (path) at 50°, to collect experimental data for the utilisation of geothermal energy at Puga for commercial exploitation of the brine. It was observed that as compared to solar evaporation which takes 40 days, the crystallisation took only 7 days. It has also been established that the crystallisation route is similar to D'ans isotherm at 55° for Na₂SO₄-K₂SO₄-MgSO₄-Na₂Cl₂-K₂Cl₂-H₂O system. In the present system, thenardite is crystallised out with glaserite and astrakanite followed by leonite, kainite, sylvinit and carnallite. Crystallisation ends in kieserite.

TSOKAR lake, (altitude 16000 ft, AMSL) has an area of about 13 sq km, the brine consisting chiefly of sulphates and chlorides of sodium, potassium and magnesium. When the lake brine is subjected to evaporation, various combination of salt minerals separate out. The specific salt combination that separate out is a function of density and temperature of the brine, pressure being always atmospheric. The data on this systematic separation of the salts from the brine in equilibrium at a specific temperature, establishes crystallisation behaviour (path) of the brine at that temperature. This in turn will help in extraction of the desired salts and also any improvement in the quality of the recovered salts. Crystallisation behaviour of the lake brine with solar evaporation is already established¹. Adjacent to Tsokar, there is a valley known as Puga, where India's most promising geothermal fields (hot springs) lie. Since it takes more than 40 days to complete one set of experiment with solar evaporation and also keeping in view the availability of geothermal fluids at Puga, an attempt has been made in this investigation to study the crystallisation behaviour of the brine on evaporation at 50°.

Experimental

The lake brine (density 21.8° Bé) (20 dm³) having composition, Cl⁻, 6.73; Mg²⁺, 1.31; Na⁺, 5.00; K⁺, 1.87; B₄O₇²⁻, 0.52%, was subjected to evaporation at 50° in an open stainless steel container. Five salt crops were collected at 34.6, 35.3, 36.6 and 37.45° Bé for en mass crystallisation. It took seven days for completion of this set of experiment. The reduction in volume and weight of the deposited salt crop separated with change in density was recorded (Table 1). The data regarding chemical composition of the deposited salts in equilibrium with brine, with change in density of the brine on evaporation were recorded (Table 2). The crops were analysed by the usual method of

analysis²—sulphate by barium chloride, chloride by silver nitrate, sodium and potassium by flame photometer, magnesium by EDTA, and borate by neutralisation method. The mineralogical compositions (Table 3) of salt crops were worked out.

TABLE 1—FRACTION OF SALT COLLECTED AT DIFFERENT DENSITIES

Density	Reduction	Fraction	Weight of
η	in	of salt	salt collected
°Bé	volume	collected	kg
1.316	13.900	500-1	0.170
1.324	2.200	500-2	1.282
1.340	0.600	500-3	1.430
1.350	2.900	500-4	2.200
—	En mass	500-5	1.120

Quantity of brine taken = 20 dm³.

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SALT FRACTIONS

Salt fraction	Sod. sulphate %	Pot. sulphate %	Mag. sulphate %	Sod. chloride %	Pot. chloride %	Mag. chloride %	Sod. borate %
50C-1	40.87	6.55	21.68	15.79	—	—	0.31
50C-2	85.14	2.78	3.46	5.47	—	—	0.51
50C-3	29.56	5.01	14.35	35.76	—	—	0.77
50C-4	—	17.97	21.53	43.15	2.74	—	1.82
50C-5	—	—	23.98	24.12	19.06	5.09	5.72

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) curves of salt crops were recorded on a MOM derivatograph (Hungary); the reference material used being anhydrous reagent grade Al₂O₃, and the thermocouple was platinum—platinum-rhodium. Salt crops for thermal analysis were ground (just before the thermal analysis) to pass 150 mesh ISS sieve.

Results and Discussion

With evaporation of brine at 50° from start till the brine achieves density of 36.6° Bé (50C-3), the

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TABLE 3—MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SALT FRACTIONS

Salt fraction	Thenerdite %	Glaserite %	Astrakanite %	Halite %	Sylvinite %	Leonite %	Kainite %	Carnallite %	Kieserite %	Sodium borate pentahydrate %	Free moisture %	Total
50C-1	13.58	8.92	60.08	15.73	—	—	—	—	—	0.45	1.88	99.99
50C-2	80.31	3.53	9.60	5.47	—	—	—	—	—	0.73	0.02	99.66
50C-3	11.27	6.97	39.86	35.76	—	—	—	—	—	1.01	5.31	99.58
50C-4	—	—	—	43.15	—	37.80	9.81	—	5.40	2.63	1.43	99.54
50C-5	—	—	—	12.30	26.90	—	—	14.84	27.56	8.29	9.63	99.62

major salt separated is sodium sulphate (sodium salt) along with magnesium sulphate. The maximum potassium ion separated in these first three salt fractions (upto 36.6° Bé, *i.e.* 50C-3) is 2.94%, and immediately after this density, the potassium ion separated in the salt fractions increases rapidly to 9.50 and 10.00% (in 50C-4 and 50C-5). That is, major portion of sodium sulphate is separated upto 36.6° Bé followed by major potassium salts (potassium sulphate and potassium chloride) till completion of evaporation. The probable mineralogical composition of the salt fractions (Table 3) shows that thenerdite and astrakanite with glaserite crystallise first followed by leonite and kainite. This is then followed by the crystallisation of kieserite type of salts.

In salt fractions 50C-1, 50C-2 and 50C-3, astrakanite present is 60.08, 9.60 and 39.86%, respectively (Table 3). In DTA studies, the endothermic effect of astrakanite at 110° due to dehydration and transformation to loweite, is observed at 100, 125 and 100° in 50C-1, 50C-2 and 50C-3, respectively. The low value of the peak temperature in 50C-1 and 50C-3, is due to the presence of other salts, other than mirabilite/thenerdite in the salt fraction, and high value of the peak temperature in 50C-2 is due to the presence of mirabilite/thenerdite in the salt fraction⁸. The endothermic effect at 220° due to complete dehydration of astrakanite is observed at 185, 180 and 185° in 50C-1, 50C-2 and 50C-3, respectively. The low value of the peak temperature is due to admixture of mirabilite and glaserite. The endothermic effect of astrakanite is shown at 570, 570 and 575° in 50C-1, 50C-2 and 50C-3, respectively; this endotherm being due to decomposition of astrakanite and well resolved in 50C-1 and 50C-3. The presence of thenerdite is also shown by the DTA studies. The endothermic effect due to polymorphic transformation of thenerdite is observed at 270° in 50C-1, 50C-2 and 50C-3, and is well resolved in 50C-1 and 50C-3. The presence of glaserite is, however, not indicated by DTA in these salt fractions which is due to low concentration of this salt mineral in these salt fractions.

In the salt fraction 50C-4, leonite and sodium chloride predominate with kainite and kieserite. No thermal effect is observed due to kainite and kieserite, instead there is only one thermal effect

due to leonite which is observed at 635° and is due to polymorphic transformation of leonite. In the salt fraction 50C-5, kieserite and carnallite predominate with sodium chloride and sylvinite. The presence of carnallite is confirmed by DTA studies. The endothermic effect observed at 150 and 175° is due to melting and boiling off of the solution (reported value of peak temperature 160–165° due to melting; 190° due to boiling off of solution⁹). The endothermic effect observed at 220° is due to dehydration of carnallite and at 455° due to melting of carnallite (the reported⁹ values of these endothermic peaks are 230 and 425°, respectively). The thermal effect due to kieserite is also observed. The endotherm at 340° due to dehydration of kieserite is observed at 315° and is not well resolved. Beside above peaks due to thermal effects in the DTA, there is an endothermic effect at 625° which may be attributed to polymorphic transformation of leonite formed due to heating in the experimental run.

From Table 3, it is evident that crystallisation follows a specific route. Thenerdite is the first to crystallise, with glaserite and astrakanite. This is followed by leonite, kainite, sylvinite and carnallite. Crystallisation ends in kieserite. Sodium chloride and sodium borate are crystallised invariably throughout the crystallisation route. This crystallisation route is similar to D'ans isotherm⁴ at 55° for $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\text{—K}_2\text{SO}_4\text{—MgSO}_4\text{—Na}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{—K}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{—MgCl}_2\text{—H}_2\text{O}$ system, except a few phases, *viz.* vanthoffite, langbenite and leonite which are actually surpassed in this system due to forced evaporation. By attempting evaporation of Tsokar lake brine at 50°, not only the number of days for completion of one set of experiment is reduced from 40 to 7 days, but also, there is resolution of sodium salt (sodium sulphate) and potassium salts (potassium sulphate/potassium chloride) which in turn will help in further processing of these salts for getting single or double salts of industrial utility. Besides, this also gives data for the utilisation of geothermal energy for commercial exploitation of the Tsokar lake brine.

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